

Table 2 Summary of the most productive authors in research quality and transparency in applied linguistics research.

Author	Year 1st pub.	TP	h-index	TC	Current affiliation	Country
Plonsky, L	2010	14	11	2051	Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, AZ	United States
Oswald, F L	2010	2	2	1650	Rice University, Houston, TX	United States
Zhang, X	2019	2	2	377	Harbin Institute of Technology	China
Cristia, A	2018	3	3	348	École Normale Supérieure, Paris	France
Frank, M C	2018	3	2	309	Stanford University, Stanford, CA	United States
Bergmann, C	2018	2	2	308	Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics	Germany
Peters, E	2019	3	3	217	Ghent University	Belgium
Keren-Portnoy, T	2020	2	2	210	University of York	United Kingdom
Havron, N	2020	2	2	196	University of Haifa	Israel
Tsui, A S M	2020	1	1	192	University of Hong Kong	Hong Kong
Al-Hoorie, A H	2020	5	4	188	Royal Commission for Jubail and Yanbu	Saudi Arabia
Marsden, E	2018	2	2	140	University of York	United Kingdom
Derrick, D J	2016	2	2	126	University of British Columbia	Canada
Bulté, B	2019	2	2	123	Universiteit Antwerpen	Belgium
Hiver, P	2020	4	3	113	Florida State University, Tallahassee, FL	United States